

Fixed Point and Common Fixed Point Theorem for Multivalued Mappings for Banach Space

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 26 December 2022	In this Paper we will investigate some fixed point and common fixed point theorem for multivalued mappings of Banach space. We show that an extended form of many Known results taking multivalued mappings and inequities. The general form of a result proved by Banach Space and
Corresponding Author: Sandhya Singh	Convergence for multivalued mappings in fixed point and common fixed point which contains new generalized form of Theorem.
KEYWORDS: Banach space, Normed Banach space, fixed point, Common fixed point, uniformly convex, multivalued mapping, fejer monotone.	

1. INTRODUCTION

Let E be a non-empty compact Convex. subset of uniformal convex Banach Space X and T is a self map
Then $T: E \rightarrow E$ is called multivalued non-expansive mapping
If

$$\|T_s - T_t\| \leq \|s, t\| \quad \forall s, t \in E$$

Since X is a unifomaly conver then every non-expansive mapping

$T: E \rightarrow E$ has a fixed point (see **Browder** [5] Kirk [1] [6] [7])gives the Comprehensive survey Concerning. A fixed point theorem for non-expansive mappings.

and (Dwivedi, Bhardwaj, Shrivastava [13]) worked for Common fixed theorems in Banach space.

Here N is a set of all positive integers and $F(T)$ is a set of all fixed point of a mapping T .

Then $F(T) = \{S \in E: T_S = S\}$ and if $S_0 \in E$ then $\{S_n\}$ in E defined as

$$\begin{cases} S_{n+1} = (1 - \alpha_n)T_{S_n} + \alpha_n T_{y_n} \\ t_n = (1 - \beta_n)u_n + \beta_n T_{u_n} \\ u_n = (1 - \delta_n)S_n + \delta_n T_{S_n} \end{cases} \quad (1.1)$$

Where $\{\alpha_n\}, \{\beta_n\}$ and $\{\delta_n\}$ are sequence in $(0,1)$
we write some definitions Before start the main result.

2. PRELIMINARIES

Definition 2.1: A multivalued mapping $T: E \rightarrow CB(E)$ is Called non-expansive if

$$H(T_s, T_t) \leq \|s - t\| \quad \forall s, t \in E$$

Definition 2.2: A sequence $\{S_n\}: n \in N$ in X is Called fejer monotone w.r. to subset E of X if

$$\|S_{n+1} - p\| \leq \|S_n - p\| \quad \forall p \in E \text{ and } n \geq 1$$

Example 2.3: Suppose E is a non-empty subset of X then $T: E \rightarrow E$ is a quasi-non expansive mapping then the sequence $\{S_n\}$ defined of $S_{n+1} = T_n$ is fejer monotone w.r. to $F(I)$

Definition 2.4: Let E is a non-empty subset of X . $\{S_n\}$ is a fejer monotone sequence w.r. to E then -

- (i) The sequence $\{S_n\}$ is Bounded
- (ii) And for every $S \in E \{\|S_n - S\|\}$ is converges.

Definition 2. 5: [3] A Banach space X is satisfy the condition if For any sequence $\{S_n\}$ in X $S_n \rightarrow S \Rightarrow \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sup \|S_n - S\| \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sup \|S_n - t\| \quad \forall t \in E$ with $t \neq S$

Definition 2. 6: [15] Let E is a subset of X and A multivalued non-expansive mapping

$T: E \rightarrow CB(E)$ is satisfy the condition If \exists a non decreasing function.

$$\begin{aligned} F: [0, \infty) &\rightarrow [0, \infty) \text{ with } f(0) = 0 \\ f(r) &> 0 \quad \forall r \in [0, \infty) \end{aligned}$$

Such that $D(X, T_S) \geq f(D(X, F(T))) \quad \forall S \in E$

Lemma 2. 7: [15] Suppose that X be a unifarmaly convex Banach space and

$$0 \leq p \leq x_n \leq q \leq 1 \quad \forall n \in N$$

$\{S_n\}$ and $\{t_n\}$ are two sequences of X

Then

$$\begin{aligned} \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|S_n\| &\leq r \\ \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|t_n\| &\leq r \end{aligned}$$

and also $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n S_n + (1 - x_n)t_n\| = r \forall r > 0$

Then

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \|S_n - t_n\| = 0 \tag{2.1}$$

3. MAIN RESULT

Let X be a Normed Banach space and E be a non-empty closed and convex subset of X and T is. self mapping

Then $T: E \rightarrow P(E)$ is multivalued mapping

Let $\{S_n\}$ is a sequence in $P(E)$ defined as

$$\begin{cases} S_{n+1} &= (1 - \alpha_n)x_n + \alpha_n y_n \\ t_n &= (1 - \beta_n)a_n + \beta_n z_n \\ u_n &= (1 - \delta_n)s_n + \delta_n x_n \end{cases} \tag{3.1}$$

Where $x_n \in T_{s_n}, y_n \in T_{t_n}$ and $z_n \in T_{u_n}$ and $\{\alpha_n\}, \{\beta_n\}, \{\delta_n\}$ are sequences in $(0,1)$

Theorem 3.1. Let X be a uniformly convex Banach space and E be a non-empty Closed Convex subset of X and T is a self map.

Then $T: E \rightarrow p(E)$ be a multivalued mapping.

such that $F(T) \neq \psi$ and P_T be a nonexpansive mapping

$$P_T P = \{P\} \forall P \in F(T)$$

The sequence $\{S_n\}$ defined in (3.1) Now we have to prove

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} D(S_n; T_{S_n}) = 0$$

Proof: By using definition 2.2

$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|S_n - p\|$ exist for $p \in F(T)$

Let

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|S_n - p\| = c \geq 0$$

if $e = 0$

$$\begin{aligned} D(S_n, T_{S_n}) &\leq \|S_n - x_n\| \leq \|S_n - p\| + \|x_n - p\| \\ &\leq \|S_n - p\| + H(P_T S_n; P_T P) \\ D(S_n, T_{S_n}) &\leq \|S_n - P\| + \|S_n - p\| \\ &\leq (2) \|S_n - p\| \\ &\rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty \end{aligned}$$

Then $c = 0$ if $c \geq 0$

From (3.1)

$$\|S_{n+1} - p\| = \|(1 - \alpha_n)x_n + \alpha_n y_n - p\| \tag{3.2}$$

After solving (3.2)

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq (1 - \alpha_n)\|x_n - p\| + \alpha_n\|y_n - p\| \\ &\leq (1 - \alpha_n)H(P_T S_n, P_T p) + \alpha_n H(P_T t_n, P_T p) \\ &\leq (1 - \alpha_n)\|S_n - p\| + \alpha_n\|t_n - p\| \end{aligned}$$

Using (2.1) we get

$$\|S_{n+1} - p\| \leq \|t_n - p\| \tag{3.3}$$

Similarl from (3.1)

$$\|t_n - p\| \leq \|u_n - p\| \tag{3.4}$$

and

$$\|u_n - p\| \leq \|S_n - p\| \tag{3.5}$$

(a). Taking sup lim on both side (3.5) we get

$$\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|u_n - p\| \leq c \tag{3.6}$$

(b). Taking sup lim on both side (3.4) we get

$$\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|t_n - p\| \leq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|u_n - p\| \leq C \tag{3.7}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now } \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - p\| &\leq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} H(P_T S_n, P_T p) \\ &\leq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|S_n - p\| \end{aligned} \tag{3.8}$$

$$\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - p\| \leq C \tag{3.9}$$

and using (3.7) we have

$$\begin{aligned} \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|y_n - p\| &\leq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|h_n - p\| \\ \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|y_n - p\| &\leq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} H(P_T t_n, P_T p) \\ &\leq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|t_n - p\| \leq C \end{aligned} \tag{3.10}$$

Since we know that

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|\alpha_n(x_n - p) + (1 - \alpha_n)(y_n - p)\| \\ = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|S_{n+1} - p\| = c. \end{aligned}$$

It follows Lemma (2.7) we have

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|S_n - t_n\| = 0 \tag{3.11}$$

From 3.2 we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|S_{n+1} - p\| &= \|(1 - \alpha_n)x_n + \alpha_n y_n - p\| \\ \Rightarrow \|S_n - p\| &= \frac{\|S_n - p\| - \|S_{n+1} - p\|}{\alpha_n} + \|t_n - p\| \end{aligned} \tag{3.12}$$

Taking inf lim on both side 3.12 we get

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \inf \|S_n - p\| &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \inf \frac{\|S_n - p\| - \|S_{n+1} - p\|}{\alpha_n} + \|t_n - p\| \\ e &\leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \inf \|t_n - p\| \end{aligned} \tag{3.13}$$

From (3.7) and (3.13) we get

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|t_n - p\| = c$$

It follows Lemma 2.7 we have

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|u_n - z_n\| = 0 \tag{3.14}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Since } \|t_n - p\| &= \|(1 - \beta_n)\mu_n + \beta_n z_n - p\| \\ &\leq (1 - \beta_n)\|u_n - p\| + \beta_n\|z_n - u_n\| \end{aligned}$$

Applying (3.14) we get

$$\|t_n - p\| \leq \|u_n - p\| \tag{3.15}$$

Taking inf lim on both side (2.15) we get

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \inf \|t_n - p\| &\leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \inf \|u_n - p\| \\ c &\leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \inf \|u_n - p\| \end{aligned} \tag{3.16}$$

From (3.6) and (3.16)

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|u_n - p\| = C$$

It follows Lemma 2.7 we have

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|S_n - x_n\| = 0$$

Since

$$D(S_n, T_{S_n}) \leq \|S_n - x_n\|$$

Hence

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} D(S_n, T_{S_n}) = 0 \tag{3.17}$$

(3.17) is the proved of our theorem.

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REFERENCES

1. W.A. Kirk, "A. Fixed point theorems For mappings do not increase distance" Amer. Math. monthly 72(1965)1004 – 1006
2. E.F. Browder, "Non- expansive non- linear operators in Banach "spaces" proc. Not. Acad. sci. U.S.A. 54(1965) 104I-1044
3. Z. Opial, "Weak convergence of the sequence of successive approximations for non- expansive mappings, Bull. Amer. Math. Soc. 73(1967) 591 – 597
4. Jr. W.G. Dtsen "Fixed point of quasi-non-expansive mapping" T. Austral. Math. Soc. 13(1972)167-172
5. F.E. Browder; Nonlinear equation of evaluation in Banach space in: Proc. symp. Pure math. Vol 18 amen math. Soc. Providence RI, (1976)
6. W.A kirk" "Fixed point theorem for non-expansive Mapping" Lecture notes in Math. speringer - verlag, Berlin and New York 886(1981)111 – 120
7. W.A. Kirk" Fixed point..theorem for non-expansive mappings" Contem Math. 18. (1983) 121 – 140,
8. M.R. singh and A.K.Chatterjee "Fixod point theorem in Banach spaces". Pere math. manu script 6(1987)53 – 61
9. H.K. Pathak and A.R. mailly "A Fxed point theorem in Banach spaces" Acta. Ciencia Indica17(1991) 137-139
10. N.A. Qureshi and B. singh "A Fixed point theorem in Banach spaces" Acta ciencia Indica 17(1991)282 – 284
11. P.L. Rajput, and N. Naroliya, "Fixed point theorem in Banech spaces" Acta ciencia Indica 17(1991)469 – 474
12. R.N.Yavada S.S. Rajput and R.K. Bhardwaj some fixed point and common fixed point theorems in Banach spaces" Acta Ciencia Indica 33No. 2 (2007)
13. Sabhakant Dwivedi, Ramakant Bhardwaj, Rajesh shrivastaiva." Common fixed point theorems for two mapping in 2-Banach spaces" Int. Jour. Of Math. Analysis 3(2009)889 – 896
14. R. Shrivastava, S. Dwivedi S. Rajput "Some. Fixed point theorems in Banach spaces" Int. Jour. of Math. sce. & Engg. Appls. 5 (2011)
15. S.H. Khan and I. Yildirim,"Approximating fixed point of Non-expansive mappings in Banach space. Fixed point theory anel App. 2012: 73 (2012)
16. S. sharma and Bhagwan "ACommon fixed point theorems on Normed space" Acta . ciencia Indica 31(2013)20 – 24
17. D.P. Shukla, Vived Tiwari, Ruchira singh "Noor Iterative processes for multivalued mappings in Banach space. Int. Jour. of matt. Analysis vol of (2014) no. 14, 6ug-657
18. A. Ahmad and M. Shakil "Some fixed point theorems in Banach space" Nonlinear Funct. Anal. & Appl. 11 (2016) 243-349
19. J.K.K, S. Dashpurte, W.H.L. "Approximation of Axed point for multivalued non-expansive mappings in Banach space" Glo. Jour. Of pure and App. Math 12(2016)4901 – 4912